

**HISTORY OF TEACHER TRAINING PROCESS IN SOUTH
UZBEKISTAN
(IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE 20-30S OF THE 20TH CENTURY)**

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Abstract. In this article, the processes of teacher training for Soviet schools established in the southern regions of Uzbekistan in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century were highlighted.

Key words: People's Union Republic of Bukhara, Cultural Revolution, Bolshevik Party, pedagogical courses, technical school, first level schools.

One of the most complicated periods of our past history is the 20-30s of the 20th century. The Bolshevik Party, which came to power, developed measures to promote its ideology and instill it in the minds of our people. The "Cultural Revolution" event was developed and the formation of the Soviet education system, considered one of the urgent tasks of cultural construction, was carried out. During this period, the activities of the educational institutions of the national education system in the country were restricted under various pretexts. As a result, measures were taken to expand the Soviet education system. During this period, the main problem in the Soviet education system was the issue of teacher training. Because the lack of teaching staff in the established Soviet schools hindered the expansion of the activities of these educational institutions. To prevent this situation, the Soviet state paid special attention to the issue of teacher training. During this period, the southern regions of Uzbekistan were part of the PURB (People's Union Republic of Bukhara).

In the middle of 1921, educational departments were established in the cities and districts of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic, including Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions[1:346]. This year, the first Soviet school was opened in East Bukhara by the People's Commissariat of Education. In 1922-1923, their number reached 73. In particular, 10 schools in Karshi, 3 in Termiz, 5 in Shahrhisabz, and 5 in Guzor were launched. During this period, there were two teachers' institutes and several pedagogical courses in the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic. These educational institutions could not provide the schools at that time with sufficient teaching personnel. Due to the fact that the former Soviet state immediately began to create a comprehensive education system in order to implement its policy, the teacher paid special attention to the training of personnel and developed the necessary measures. Short-term pedagogical courses were opened in order to quickly solve the work of teacher training. Such courses were organized not only in cities, but also in district centers. Teachers working in Soviet schools in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya, which are part of the Republic of Bukhara, graduated from these courses. Pedagogical courses usually opened at the end of the academic year, in the spring, and lasted 4-5 months until late autumn. Due to the fact that people from different categories studied in the courses, more importance was given to educational work. In such short-term courses, it was difficult to train fully mature personnel and provide theoretical and practical skills necessary for work activities. Pedagogical courses have been launched in various regions of the republic in order to ensure the quantitative growth of teaching staff in line with the Soviet education system.

In the southern regions, 31 teachers worked in the academic year 1922-1923, and in the academic year 1925-1926, their number reached 143. [2:61] Similar courses were organized in the cities of Karshi and Termiz. This year, 80% of teachers in Uzbekistan studied in short-term courses. [3:114] Lack of classrooms, teaching tools, textbooks, and qualified pedagogues for students studying in the course. had a negative impact on the quality of education. At the end of 1926, the number of

students was reduced to 30 people due to the difficulty of financially supporting the pedagogical course in Karshi. [4:112] Twelve students of the pedagogical course in Karshi were sent to Fergana to continue their studies. In the pedagogical courses, the teachers improved their knowledge and skills and received a permit to work in schools. However, even in this way, it was not possible to meet the need for teaching staff. For this reason, teaching personnel from Bukhara, Tashkent and other cities were constantly sent to Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions.

In 1925, 27, in 1928, 30, and in 1929-1930 academic year, 100 people who graduated from secondary and higher educational institutions were sent to Kashkadarya region to become teachers. But due to the lack of favorable conditions for them, they had to leave the schools after working for a couple of years. This would not solve the problem of shortage of personnel in the south of Uzbekistan, but would put on the agenda the need to use internal opportunities for personnel training. In order to solve this vital problem, the local leaders decided to send the children of the indigenous people to study in other cities. 168 people from Kashkadarya region in 1926. 135 young people from Surkhandarya region were sent to study in Moscow, Leningrad, Tashkent, Samarkand and Fergana. Among them were personnel in the pedagogical direction.

In the 1925-1926 academic year, a course for retraining first-level school teachers was organized in Tashkent for 135 places.[5:67] In the course, teachers from schools of Khorezm and Surkhandarya regions were retrained. The qualification of teachers of Kashkadarya region was increased in the 100-seat course organized in Fergana. It was not possible to train competent pedagogues in the courses organized out of necessity. In those years, the periodical press published articles and reports with the title "Anyone can become a teacher in literacy schools, as long as he is literate." The publication of such messages in the press or the forced orientation to teaching led to a cold approach to the task of teaching.

In the 1925-1926 school year, there were 1895 teachers who studied in republican courses. 279 of them were women, 139 belonged to the local nationality.

In those years, the lack of personnel in the schools of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions made the leadership of the republic tasked with opening teacher-training educational institutions in the southern regions.

In 1927, according to the decision of the People's Commissariat of Education of Uzbekistan, educational institutes of pedagogy were established in the cities of Karshi and Termiz. The lack of classrooms and teachers in the newly established pedagogic educational institutions had a negative impact on the satisfactory education of students. The teachers who teach in the lands of knowledge are mainly those who have a secondary education and graduated from the technical school of education in Tashkent. Nevertheless, Karshi, Termiz educational institutes of pedagogy and pedagogic courses, which were opened out of necessity, have overcome existing difficulties and made a significant contribution to the process of providing teachers to schools located in the south of Uzbekistan.

In the 1927-1928 academic year, 43 people graduated from the pedagogic course in Termiz and were sent to work in rural schools. Also, 27 teachers completed retraining courses. In the above years, there were 53 people studying at the Termiz Pedagogical University and the pedagogical course, 11 of them were women. [7:30] The number of teachers working in the schools of Kashkadarya region in this academic year was 103. Although the number of teachers increased compared to previous years, it was not enough. The schools in the southern regions are provided with highly educated teachers mainly by pedagogical institutes in the cities of Tashkent, Samarkand, and Bukhara, and partly by teachers who studied in the cities of Fergana, Moscow, and Leningrad. In the early years, insufficient attention was paid to attracting representatives of the local population to educational institutions, so there were many difficulties in providing the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions with highly educated teaching staff.

In 1928, 242 teachers worked in the schools of Kashkadarya region, only 2 of them had higher education. The lack of highly educated teachers limited the possibility of conducting the teaching system in schools in an exemplary manner.

Most of the existing teachers were trained in the following years, and some of them were not able to perform even simple calculations. In the following years, that is, in the 1934-1935 school year, the number of highly educated teachers in Kashkadarya region was 14. , even if it was opened, the readings would not be carried out satisfactorily. Teachers in the schools of the southern regions of Uzbekistan were trained in professional development courses organized mainly in the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara, Fergana, and Tashkent.

So, in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, the activities of the institutions of the national education system in the regions of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya were restricted. The Soviet education system was created and their activities were expanded. Pedagogical courses were organized in order to provide teaching staff to schools in the southern regions of Uzbekistan. In the years before the Second World War, educational institutes of pedagogy operated in the cities of Karshi and Termiz. The issue of providing highly educated medical staff has been complicated.

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